

Paper 4

EXPLORING INSTITUTIONAL VALUES AND BEST PRACTICES ACROSS SELECT SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY AFFILIATE COLLEGES

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Abstract:

Assessment and Accreditation is deeply utilized for determining the “Quality Status” of a Higher Educational Institution (HEI). HEI denotes here in particular a College, a University, or any other recognised Unit therein. Meeting the standards of quality set by NAAC (National Assessment & Accreditation Council) is absolutely essential for the HEI in terms of its educational processes and outcomes, research, infrastructure, learning resources, organisation, governance, financial well-being and student services. NAAC is an autonomous body established by UGC (University Grants Commission) for the purpose. Therefore, with a view to understand the specific organization and governance aspects of select Srinivas university affiliate colleges, in relation to a particular NAAC Self Study process we have undertaken a study here to explore its institutional values & best practices followed. In this paper, we have researched social responsibilities, good practices, institutional distinctiveness and other relevant aspects to present before our stakeholders [1].

Keyword: Higher Educational Institution (HEI), Best Academic Practices, Quality Teaching Processes, Institutional Values, Srinivas University, NAAC, UGC

I. Introduction:

Adhering to the benchmarks of quality set by NAAC (National Assessment & Accreditation Council) is necessary for the HEI in present academic environment in India. These standards are in terms of educational processes and outcomes, research, infrastructure, learning resources, organisation, governance, financial well-being and student services. Srinivas

University, a well-known state private university has colleges preparing for NAAC assessment in these regards. NAAC is an autonomous body established by UGC (University Grants Commission) for this purpose. Undertaking self-assessment for accreditation preparation has always been the part of preparation exercise in this regards. Therefore, this paper provides the stakeholders constructing self-study report steady inputs to improve the quality of report.

II. Objectives:

The primary aim of this study is to determine the present parameters available in the colleges required for NAAC Criteria. The object also further necessitates comparing with actual required benchmarks associated with the overall development of the institution resulting in sustainable development [2].

III. Research Methodology:

To conduct this study, we chose 3 Colleges of Srinivas University namely: Srinivas College of Management & Commerce, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Humanities and Social Sciences. Descriptive Investigation Technique has been employed to collect information from various colleges through direct interviews. The responses from the interviews conducted have been presented through observation process for analysis and interpretation [3].

IV. Analysis and Interpretation of Findings:

The details of responses gathered from direct interviews collected from various colleges under Srinivas university has been presented below:

(1) Gender Equity Programmes & Facilities

Periodical workshops on Girl Child discrimination, violence against women, problem on gender health and nutrition, trafficking on women has to be conducted. University/Institute level call centre must be provided as hotline for emergency to protect students. Giving more and more concession in fees in order to attract the women girl students (Socially Backward) [4].

(2) Gender Sensitivity

Workshops to be conducted for all genders on safety and security to be observed as individuals in the society. Sensitization programs on effects of ragging and anti-sexual

harassment, drugs has to deliver at a regular intervals. Self-defence training like martial arts for women for protection. Psychological counselling to be provided periodically by mentors to both genders [5]. Mentors should be professionally appointed MSW Professional Counsellors (Gender Based). Counselling record should be maintained for proof. Installation of CCTV camera outside necessary places. Provision of boy's common room could be exploratory option. Visiting wardens to hostel should be conducted once in a month to foster confidence among hostel students.

(3) Power Requirement (RE)

- Deployment of possible windmill fans for harnessing wind energy to power our resources.
- Deployment of solar panels universally to garner the sun energy to power our resources.
- Bio-gas form could be utilized to generate more power and energy.

(4) Power Requirement (LED)

Uniformification of LED lights and bulbs across all facilities of the college to save the annual lighting power requirements. Rechargeable LED bulbs could also be explored to save voltage power as well as generator load.

(5) Waste Management

Minimum 3 waste bins could be placed in each floor of the institutions.

3 coloured bins take different waste:

- Blue bin is for recyclable waste.
- Brown bin is for kitchen and garden waste.
- Green or grey bin is for non-recyclable waste.

Qualified personal with waste handling capability must be appointed to dispose all forms of solid and liquid wastes. Existing e-waste materials should be periodically sent for recycling by shredding Material and selling it for scrap [6].

(6) Rainwater Harvesting

Make the institution rooftop as catchment for collecting rainwater where it falls. In rooftop harvesting, the roof becomes the catchments, and the rainwater is collected from the roof of the institution. It can either be stored in a tank or diverted to artificial recharge system. This method is less expensive and very effective and if implemented properly helps in augmenting the groundwater level of the area.

(7) Green Practices Followed

NSS green cell to be constituted as well as student forum green cell for initiating green activities across the campus. One plant adoption for student program should be followed. (One admission one tree). Adoption of parks, relevant circle could be identified for planting saplings [7].

Major Green Campus Initiatives could be undertaken :

- Solar Power Station.
- Waste Management.
- Rain Water Harvesting.
- Recycle Bin for e-waste.
- Complete Ban on Polythene's at Campus.
- Institute Community Garden.
- Use more of LED than CFL.
- Digital Library/E-learning Centre.

(8) Facilities provided to differently abled (Divyangjan)

- Separate exam system and room should be provided for differently abled candidates.
- Emergency vehicle should station in the campus for the benefits of differently abled candidates [8].
- Trained personnel to administer the first aid in case of campus accidents.

(9) Specific Initiatives to address local advantages and disadvantages

- Proximity of geological survey of India and forum mall could be harnessed for part-time job and project work, faculty consultancy projects and Ph.D. works.
- Locational map should be displayed along with train timings, bus timings, location of paying guest, nearby hospitals, police stations, fire stations.

(10) Initiatives taken to engage with and contribute to local community

- Swatch Bharath Abhiyaan should be conducted once in a month by students to clean the surrounding of the campus. (1 hour should be reserved in a month).
- Skill India courses have is explored with unemployed youth through a workshop.
- Regular contribution to old age homes should have to be made.
- Villages and schools can be adopted to roll out social work programs.
- Red Cross – Blood Donation Camp.
- Health Check-up by Srinivas Medical College Hospital.

(11) Code of Conduct for Students & Teachers

- Dress code and Grooming.
- Time Sense and Punctuality.
- Discipline.
- Periodical Updating the rules and regulation for the greater good of institution.

(12) Inclusion of Indian Constitution & Related Subjects

- Indian constitution subjects should be mandatorily integrated into the syllabus and teaching pedagogy of all streams.
- A certificate course has to be rolled out or in this regards.
- New programmes can be started in this regards like LLB, LLM, Journalism and Media.

(13) Certificate Programme offered in Human Values and Professional Ethics [9]

- Human Rights.
- Cyber Crime workshop.
- Road Traffic Training.
- Safety and Security.
- Morale, Conduct and Behaviour.

(14) Permissions from Statutory Bodies

- UGC
- Association of Indian Universities
- AICTE

(15) Activities Conducted for the promotion of universal values

National anthem to be introduced in each class, each program in the university. NCC wing has to be introduced or inaugurated.

- Army.
- Navy.
- Air force.

(16) Efforts made in organizing national festivals and birth/death anniversaries of great Indian personalities

- Republic Day.
- Independence Day.
- Gandhi Jayanthi.

- Vivekananda Jayanthi.
- Teachers Day.

(17) Efforts towards maintenance of complete transparency in Financial, Academic, Administrative, and Auxiliary functions

- Dhi-Heraizen Academic SAAS.

(18) Best practices collected from each faculty

- Faculty Teaching Strategy.
- Innovative ways to educate the student.
- Latest syllabus which has a scope in upcoming days.

(19) Best practices successfully implemented as per NAAC Format

- Swayam Prabha – Learning Education Channel.
- SAAS – Dhi-Heraizen.
- API – Research Index.
- NPTEL – Online Learning.
- NDL – National Digital Library.
- Smart Class.
- Plagiarism Software – Faculties and Students.

(20) Institutional Performance in one area distinctive to its Vision, Priority and Thrust

High contribution towards research. Ranked among some of the prestigious Business schools in SSRN rankings. Unique conference series conducted.

V. Conclusion:

To conclude, the above study gives a bird's eye view of the necessary programmes that has to be conducted for ensuring meeting the development and sustainability standards of the colleges in meeting NAAC regulations. We are confident that study will assist the relevant decision makers of the institution to ensure the implementation of the necessary remaining criteria's for the holistic growth of the institutions towards nation building as mandated by NAAC [10].

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